

CoARA Action Plan Development Guidelines

- Final draft -

Deliverable number	D2.5
Deliverable name:	CoARA Action Plan's Development Guidelines (CoARA AP Guide)
WP number:	WP2: CoARA AP Development Support
Version	01
Delivery due date:	Project month 8 (31/07/2025)
Actual date of submission:	
Dissemination level:	Public
Number of pages:	5
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Full document available online:	10.5281/zenodo.15648857

Introduction

This document is based on the University of Rijeka (UNIRI) practices and experience and is part of the activities foreseen in the framework of the „Open Science Collaboration for Research Career Advancement and Policy Innovation at UNIRI and UCY (OSCAR)“ project co-financed by the EU Horizon Europe (HE) programme „CoARA Boost“. The document provides a set of guidelines aimed at assisting institutions in the conceptualisation, drafting, preparation and implementation effective action plans for reforming research assessment practices, aligning with the commitments set forth by the Coalition for Advancing Research Assessment (CoARA). It offers a structured approach to developing action plans that reflect institutional goals and values while adhering to CoARA's principles.

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Before Preparing an Institutional CoARA Action Plan

Premise: although national support is very important, a lot can be done at the institutional level relying on the human and material resources and the level of institutional autonomy that each research performing organisation (RPO) has.

1. Appoint a person in charge of the CoARA activities at the institution, ideally with a prominent position at the (di)rectorate, with a clear decision-making and coordination mandate. Alternatively, make sure to have a “patron” for the action, who is part of the top management of the institution. Form a dedicated team around this person, each with a clear role within the team, and encompassing researchers at various career stages as well as responsible people from the HR department, research management, the library (especially those dealing with open science) and other pertinent services (e.g. knowledge valorisation / knowledge transfer / IP services, etc.).
2. Make an in-depth analysis of the core values of your institution, based especially on the up-to-date strategy, the mission and vision statements and the relative human resources (HR) policies.
3. Analyse the relevant national acts and rules as well as the constraints they pose in relation to hiring and career progression of researchers, with special attention dedicated to the relevant criteria and the national bodies that define them (e.g. rectors’ conference, national councils, research funding organisations (RFOs) and similar).
4. List and analyse the salient features of the existing institutional policies, documents and action plans related to:
 - the participation of your institution in alliances (e.g. European University Initiative) and networks and the activities and document related to HR policies already produced in these frameworks;
 - the activities aimed at the build-up of leadership and management skills and practices;
 - the participation in the Human Resources Strategy for Researchers (HRS4R) initiative,

with:

- the up-to-date versions of the European Charter for Researchers;
 - the results of the up-to-date version of the institutional gap analysis;
 - the up-to-date version of the institutional HRS4R action plan;
 - the up-to-date version of the institutional Open, Transparent and Merit-based Recruitment (OTM-R) policy;
- the awareness, acceptance and implementation level of EU/EC initiatives such as the European Competence Framework for Researchers, the ERA Talent Platform and similar;
 - the activities related to the development of teaching practices and skills via institutionally supported initiatives and funding schemes;
 - the bylaws and practices related to ethics and research integrity (codes, involved bodies, relation to European and national rules and procedures) – considering in this framework also the latest version of the European Code of Conduct for Research Integrity;
 - the diversity, inclusivity, and gender equality plans and policies as well as, if available, provisions related to work-life balance;
 - open science (OS), including the participation of your institution in the relevant international initiatives (e.g. DORA) and/or projects, the used national or international repositories, the practices related to research data management and similar;
 - internationalization activities and provisions, and especially those related to the mobility of researchers, including your participation in Erasmus+, CEEPUS and other international fora;
 - the defined institutional criteria for mentors and supervisors (especially for doctoral students);
 - the institutional framework related to graduate studies (e.g. doctoral schools), including the regulation and practices concerning the recruitment, as well as the recognition, reward, and incentive practices for early career researchers (ECRs);
 - open innovation and knowledge valorisation practices, including the provisions related to IPR, the establishment of spin-offs and start-ups, as well as the incentives (including financial) for researchers participating in these activities) – all related also to the European, national, and/or regional and institutional smart specialization, economic development and similar strategies and policies;
 - science outreach practices and their recognition and reward.
5. Analyse the current institutional practices and provisions related to the management structure and decision-making, the counselling and operative bodies and expert councils that participate in the decision-making processes, the inclusion of the researchers at various career stages (R1, R2, R3 and R4) in these councils and in decision- and policy-making in general.
 6. Clearly define your own institutional research assessment strategic priorities and goals, as well as their relation to the CoARA commitments.

Preparing the CoARA Action Plan

7. Based on the above analyses, draft the CoARA Action Plan (AP), thereby clearly defining:
- **Why engaging in it:** clearly state the case why is it institutionally, but also at the level of the constituents of the institution and for the individual researchers, important to be part of CoARA, i.e., what will the actual gains for the institutional stakeholders be. Explain / reaffirm especially that everyone should be aware that:
 - Research assessment is a crucial quality assurance process that guarantees the creation of new knowledge as well as meeting economic and societal needs.
 - Research assessment has to be responsible, equitable, transparent, efficient, and sustainable.
 - The current system is based on assessing the quantity and the publication vehicle and not the actual quality or real usefulness of the performed research, while it also does not take into account all the varied aspects of the research activities (diversity!), herein including social and public accountability and responsibility.
 - The current system is not aligned with the evolving research process, i.e., the rapid development of open science and the digital transition (AI), nor with the need to develop the transferrable skills of researchers (communication, leadership, teamwork, management, organisation) – having here especially in mind the precarity of ECRs’ careers and the evident development of multi-, inter- and transdisciplinarity, as well as of the intersectoral and interoperable mobility.
 - Per definition, science is a global (open) endeavour, where the researchers themselves perform a huge portion of the research work (incl. publishing), while the publishers (especially the large ones) profit from it. In fact, the current publishing system generates many evident issues (incl. the unsustainably rising costs).
 - A dedicated AP help structuring and monitoring the process of reforming research assessment.
 - **How:** explain that the institutional activities related to CoARA will induce an evolutionary (not revolutionary) change of the current practices that have clear shortcomings (list them while evidence their drawbacks – again for the whole institution, for the constituents and for the researchers themselves). Explain that being among the numerous institutions dealing with the process and being at the table where the decisions are made has several advantages (once more, this has to be clearly stated and based on evidence), among which are:
 - The changes are aimed at rewarding the indisputable diversity of contributions of the researchers that so far were not properly acknowledged, thus contributing to the change of the internal institutional culture.
 - The new system will provide a positive impact towards the institutional strategic research and academic goals, while catalysing and incentivising the existing institutional activities.
 - The process will promote the needed changes at the national and international (alliances/networks you are involved in) levels, thus also promoting the visibility of your own institution.
- What is more, institutionally the process should be participatory (involving researchers at all career stages (especially ECRs), but also research managers and librarians),

collaborative, coordinated, transparent, opened, and flexible, with strong leadership support and devoted resources, acknowledging the diversity of roles, career stages and disciplines.

- **What:** clearly define the actions that will be taken and how they will contribute to the CoARA commitment/goals and to your institutional (strategic, research and HR) goals. If possible, complement this with clear connection to already adopted policies and practices (OS, HRS4R, and similar). Do imperatively include among the defined actions awareness raising campaigns as well workshops and training activities aimed at upgrading the skills of the involved people.
 - **Who:** clearly define the responsible bodies and people for each and every of the foreseen actions.
 - **When:** clearly define the foreseen terms to complete each action. In this respect, group the actions in short-, medium- and longer-term.
 - **Where:** if appropriate, state whether some actions will be based on collaborations with external stakeholders, or maybe at some will be decentralised or otherwise placed in distant units or units that are not explicitly under the guidance of the institution itself and/or of its constituents.
8. While working on the AP draft, define also a clear decision-making path for its adoption and implementation, including all the phases of the AP approval, and a clear communication plan for it.
 9. Present the draft AP at the relevant internal management and decision-making, counselling and operative bodies and expert councils, and assure its approval in the rectorate and at the Senate (or, depending on the type of institution, other comparable highest participatory decision-making institutional bodies).
 10. Open a public consultation process and organize a series of presentations where the researchers (again at all career stages) in favour of CoARA and the institutional AP present it in various internal fora. If possible, invite colleagues who are already engaged in CoARA (e.g. from the European University alliance or other pertinent networks and projects the institution is involved in) to present their good practices and the results they have achieved.
 11. Dedicate the necessary resources (with a clear plan & budget), a have a clear stakeholders' engagement (RM, library, ...) plan for the AP implementation.
 12. Be aware that the implementation phase will have to be flexible and adaptable (incl. in the set time-plans).
 13. Collect and summarize the results of the public consultations, clearly stating which changes/suggestions have been adopted and which have not, with a clear justification for each of them.
 14. Use the above inputs and the planned implementation steps to prepare the final version of the institutional CoARA AP.
 15. Submit the final AP for approval by all relevant bodies (including again the highest participatory decision-making one).

Implementing the CoARA Action Plan

16. Openly publish the adopted CoARA AP, both via the internal communication channels and on a broader scale (e.g. via Zenodo).
17. Setup an institutional system to regularly collect and monitor data on how the AP is being implemented, hereby using modern digital tools (e.g., online dashboards, data collection platforms, or a suitable project management software). Distribute clearly this task among the team members.
18. Define the frequency for issuing the implementation reports, thoroughly reviewing the attained results.
19. Regularly provide feedback on the implementation status to all relevant institutional stakeholders.
20. Use the review and the stakeholders' involvement to iteratively ameliorate the process.
21. During the implementation phase, engage in the CoARA working groups and network with other institutions in your European University alliance and networks/projects you are part of to exchange experiences, organising in this framework mutual learning and best practice exchange exercises.

Be aware and be prepared that in the implementation you will be confronted with several challenges, such as:

- Inertia/unwillingness/resistance to change – do foresee incentives and rewards (especially promoting the diversity of contributions and of research culture¹ in general), as well as appropriate awareness and training activities.
- Different treatment of established vs. ECRs and of various scientific disciplines – as repeatedly evidence, do actively involve researchers at all career stages.
- The change can be seen as having a negative impact on the quality of publications and/or data safety, as well as give rise to time concerns – do use evidence to prove the opposite.
- National policies can sometimes trail behind EU/EC ones – do try involving national stakeholders (including the RFOs which can support the AP implementation by dedicated measures/funds), try creating a national coordinating body, and do gain support also at international level.
- The proposed system heavily relies on peer review, which could give rise to issues related to its quality (especially in small and closed research communities) as well as, generally/globally, to peer review fatigue – do involve a broader (international) pool of reviewers and do (critically) monitor the initiatives to use AI and similar tools in some of the phases of the per review process.

Rijeka, May 5, 2025

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